

LABOR PROTECTION RULES AND INSTRUCTIONS WHEN USING COMPUTER AND ORG TECHNIQUES IN PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES, ORGANIZATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS ARE WE DOING IT RIGHT??

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ANNOTATION

This article provides instructions on labor protection for users of computers and multifunctional equipment (printers, scanners, uninterruptible power supplies and other organizational techniques). At the same time, the "On Labor Protection" of the Republic of Uzbekistan Law and Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 12, 2000 No. 267 "Revise regulations on labor protection on review and development" and No. 153 of July 20, 2010 "Labor regulations on protection on further improvement of the legal framework" In accordance with the decisions, concepts are given about the labor protection procedure in working with computers and multifunctional equipment, their technical repair and servicing.

Keywords: Computer, scanner, guide, labor protection, workplaces, enterprises, organizations and institutions.

The computer is a very important tool in our daily work activities, especially for people who do mental work. Be careful while working at the computer, do not be distracted by foreign objects and conversations, the workplace should be equipped in such a way as to exclude uncomfortable situations and long-term static stress on the body. When working on a personal computer, the possibility of simultaneously touching equipment and parts of the room or equipment connected to the ground (battery radiators, metal structures) should be excluded.

Prepare the workplace for computer operators, remove foreign objects, conduct a visual inspection of the personal computer, make sure that the electrical outlets, plugs, and electrical wires are in good working order. Connect the computer to the 220V network while holding the power plug by its case. Safety requirements aimed at eliminating the negative impact of harmful production factors on human health when working with computers and organizational equipment must be in accordance with SanQvaM No. 0224-07 of March 29, 2007 "Sanitary rules and norms for working with computers, video display terminals and organizational equipment".

The workplace in front of the screen should be quiet. In display halls, the noise caused by air conditioners, telephones, and processors should be reduced to a minimum. Noise level in the workplace No. 012001 of October 29, 2001 SanQvaM "Noise. It must be in accordance with the general safety requirements. The use of computers and multifunctional equipment should be carried out in buildings with natural and artificial lighting that meet hygienic requirements. Displays should be placed in the north, north-east or north-west of buildings and rooms. Work areas should not be less than 4.5 m² per employee.

For computer users, the size of the desktop should be determined based on the size of the computer screen. In general, the length of the table is 160 cm; width should be 0.90 m. The distance between the desktops on which the monitors are installed (in the direction of the back surface of one monitor and the screen of the other monitor) should be at least 2.0 m, and the distance between the side surfaces of the monitors should be at least 1.2 m.

According to SES requirements for computer workers, the lighting of the workplace should be around 300 to 500 lux. The illumination of the computer screen surface should not exceed 300 lux. The light in the workplace should be proportionally distributed within the field of vision of the operator. Modern lighting should be used to illuminate the halls where the display is installed. In order for the light coming from the lamp not to be reflected on the screen, it should be placed so that the light does not fall directly on the computer screen. In order to prevent bright spots from appearing on the screen, there should be no shiny objects in the workplace, the operator's outer clothing should be of a darker color, and all objects behind him should have low brightness. When the devices are placed in a row, it is necessary to put barriers between them so that the light of the screens standing on them does not fall on each other.

The following basic safety rules should be followed when using copying and duplicating equipment: Rooms should be provided with sufficient natural and artificial light; for duplicating equipment with a volume of not less than 15 m³, the area of one workplace should be at least 6 m². The light in the workplace should be proportionally distributed within the field of vision of the operator.

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At the same time, the following are prohibited when working with copying-reproduction techniques;

- cleaning the duplicating equipment without disconnecting it from the electrical system;
 - leaning on the copy window of the copying-reproducing technique, placing the materials to be copied and other items on it;
 - using the copy-reproduction window cracked technique;
- remove jammed paper from the copier without unplugging it.

The most common occupational diseases caused by the use of computers and multifunction equipment are as follows:

- vision and eye symptoms - decreased visual acuity and relative visual threshold, false (from accommodation spasm) and true myopia, binocular (volumetric) vision is impaired, veil before the eyes, unclear contours of objects, changes in color and hako;zo;
- pain in the eyes and redness of the eyelids, crusting, frequent blinking, feeling of tiredness of the eyelids, blurred vision and hako;zo;

-drowsiness, headache in the eyebrow region (forehead), occipital and parietal regions, dizziness, pain in the limbs, fatigue, pain in the lower back, pain around the heart, shortness of breath, dryness of the skin and mucous membranes, especially dryness of the nose and throat, and hakoza;

- mental disorders and neuro-somatic diseases: anxiety, sleep disorders, narrowing of interests, memory impairment, increased number of errors, decreased targeting;

- increased incidence of bronchitis, bronchial asthma, acute respiratory diseases, neuroses, osteochondrosis;

manifestation or exacerbation of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. Such manifestations of the disease increase dramatically with an increase in computer time. In accordance with sanitary and other safety standards, the room where personal computers are located must be equipped with:

- lighting systems (natural or artificial, general or combined - if necessary);

Figure 1. Rules for proper sitting while working at the computer

The climatic conditions in the workplace of the operators must comply with the following sanitary and hygienic standards:

- relative humidity - 40-60%, but not more than 75%;

The noise level in the workplace should not exceed 50 db when the operator performs basic work on a personal computer. The order of work and rest of the operator is determined by the employer on the basis of mutual agreement in accordance with the labor laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The network agreement is determined by the collective agreement concluded between the employees of the organization and the employer, the labor contract (agreement) between the employer and the operator, or by the order of the organization.

Dielectric mats should be laid on the side of the computer power supply racks where the doors open and near the distribution board. Installation of equipment, replacement of cells and blocks must be performed with complete disconnection from the power supply. It is forbidden to connect and disconnect the disconnectors of cables connecting computers under voltage. After disconnection of the voltage, the circuit breaker will say "Do not connect!" A prohibitory poster with the inscription "People are working" should be hung. After the work is done, the person who posted this placard (or in place of it) can remove the placard and connect the voltage. When turning on the computer, the operator must connect the equipment in the following sequence:

- turn on the supply unit;
- enable peripheral devices (printer, monitor, scanner, etc.); - turn on the system unit (processor).

The operator is prohibited from starting work in the following cases:

- when a malfunction is detected in the equipment;
- in the absence of a protective earthing system in the personal computer.

A computer operator must fulfill the following requirements during work:

- to perform only the work assigned to him and received instructions;
- to keep the workplace tidy;
- keep all ventilation holes of the device open;
- use of the "mouse" external device in the presence of a special mat;
- if there is a need to stop work for a certain time, to close all active tasks in an orderly manner;
- if the operator is forced to stand directly near the monitor (at a distance of less than 2 m.) during a break during work at the computer, disconnect the source;
- therefore, at the same time, to fulfill the requirements of SanMvaQ No. 0224-07 of March 29, 2007 "Sanitary rules and norms for working in personal computers, video display terminals and office equipment" and to observe the work and rest procedures;
- to choose the physiological mode of displaying black characters on a white background when working with textual information;
- to follow the breaks during work hours and to perform the recommended exercises for the eyes, neck, arms, body and legs during physical education breaks.

The operator is prohibited from:

- touch the monitor screen and keyboard at the same time;
- touching the back panel of the system unit (processor) while the supply is connected;
- filling the upper panels of devices with paper and other objects;
- disconnection of supply during operation;
- frequent power outages;
- allowing moisture to fall on the surface of the system unit (processor), monitor, keyboard, disk drive, printer and other devices;
- connecting the equipment left in the cold (imported from outside during the winter);
- arbitrary opening and repair of equipment.

It is forbidden to leave switched-on equipment, computer devices unattended. The operator must implement the following safety requirements in the event of an accident:

If a computer malfunction occurs, the computer must be disconnected from the network. Do not try to fix the cause of the malfunction yourself, it is necessary to report it to the appropriate technical service.

In the event of a fire in an electrical cable or computer, immediately disconnect it from the network, call the fire department on 101 and extinguish the fire with a carbon dioxide or dry powder fire extinguisher. Foam fire extinguishers should not be used to extinguish electrical wiring and equipment, as foam is a good conductor of electricity. In case of electric shock, it is necessary to provide first aid to the injured person, contact a medical center or call a doctor.

When the equipment is on fire, disconnect the supply and take measures to extinguish the fire using carbon dioxide and powder fire extinguishers, call the fire safety service and report the incident to the supervisor.

The computer operator is required to perform the following tasks after the end of working hours:

- it is forbidden to disconnect the computer from the network while holding the power plug, disconnecting the computer from the power cord. When disconnecting a personal computer with a detachable power cable, first disconnect the power plug from the outlet and then the power cord from the computer;
- Tidying up the workplace;
- Cleaning the personal computer from dust should be done only after disconnecting the computer from the network;
- Cleaning the external surfaces of the computer with a soft cotton cloth slightly moistened with a neutral detergent solution (laundry soap, shampoo, etc.), in this case it is impossible to use organic solvents (acetone, gasoline, alcohol, etc.).
- Inspect and organize the workplace, put personal protective equipment in the closet, wash your face and hands with soap.
- Notify the immediate supervisor about the end of the work shift.

Computer operators are divided by the number and duration of breaks during the working day in an 8-hour shift as follows:

- For category I - 2 breaks of 15 minutes each 2 hours after the start of the shift and 2 hours after the lunch break;
- For category II - 2 hours after the start of the shift and 1.5-2 hours after the lunch break, 15 minutes each or 10 minutes for each hour of work;
- For category III - 1.5-2 hours after the start of the shift and 1.5-2 hours after the lunch break, 20 minutes each or every hour 15 minutes.

Breaks in the first 8 hours of a 12-hour shift are the same as for 8 hours of work:

- during the last 4 hours (regardless of the category and type of work) - 15 minutes every hour.

It is not recommended to work on a personal computer for more than 2 hours in a row without interruption.

References:

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